

Deliverable 5.2

Terms of Reference of EU Think Tank

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1. Context and background: FOOD 2030 and FIT4FOOD2030

In view of the global Food and Nutrition Security (FNS) challenges and the goals set in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the European Commission's (EC) Directorate General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) has established the FOOD 2030 policy framework with the objective to contribute, through research and innovation (R&I), to the transformation of European food systems to become more sustainable, resilient, responsible, diverse, inclusive and competitive.

To support the EC in the development and implementation of the FOOD 2030 policy framework and its action plan, the FIT4FOOD2030 project aims to establish a sustainable multi-stakeholder, multi-level platform, mobilizing a wide variety of stakeholders at the level of cities, regions, countries, and Europe. This platform aims (1) to make R&I policies on FNS more coherent, (2) to build competences of current and future researchers, entrepreneurs, policy-makers and society at large, and (3) to raise awareness around FOOD 2030. Overall, the project will support the urgently needed transformation of R&I on FNS by contributing to the adoption of a food system approach and a participatory and transdisciplinary approach (referred to as Responsible Research and Innovation; RRI) to R&I. The 'FOOD 2030 Platform' comprises three interlinked structures:

- A **'European Union (EU) Think Tank'**: an expert group acting as linking pin between the EC and the Policy Labs and City Labs (see below).
- **'Policy Labs'**: to establish strategic alignment and policy coherence amongst multiple stakeholders in order to inform their country's national FNS research agenda and ensure the maximum impact of research and innovation. Policy Labs will create dialogues between regional and national stakeholders along the FNS value chain, including science, industry, and consumers in various EU countries. The Policy Labs focus on concrete objectives like the development of policy briefs and research and innovation programmes.
- **'City Labs'**: to link a wide variety of actors at city level to develop hands-on informal training for students, researchers and other professionals. They will also contribute to building networks of food system actors to inform the research and innovation agenda around FNS challenges.

The aim of the EU Think Tank is to connect the EU-level with the global, national, regional and city levels. It serves as a strategic hub to work towards an integrated vision on EU food systems in a global context and the required transformation in R&I to deliver impact on the societal challenge of FNS. In this way, the EU Think Tank enables the EC to liaise with the emerging network and the lessons that FIT4FOOD2030 generates and act as a transformative network itself. It is also used as a sounding board that ensures a good connection with relevant developments, opportunities and needs on the European level and globally.

The members of the EU Think Tank have diverse backgrounds and substantial and unique expertise and knowledge (see section 8). This means the EU Think Tank adds value to the findings generated by the project and helps to translate this into EU-wide food systems and related R&I system policies and investment schemes. In this way the EU Think Tank helps to increase R&I policy coherence and alignment with the needs and expectations of the different stakeholders. Ultimately, these policies will fill the gaps identified during the project and will support the different countries to work towards a future-proof food-system.

2. The EU Think Tank: overall objectives and scope

The EU Think Tank is expected to **translate, integrate** and **transmit** the results generated by the Policy and City Labs to the EC-level, during the four project phases outlined below:

- **Phase 1: Actor identification, mobilization, system analysis (M1-12):** The EU Think Tank will, together with the Policy Labs and City Labs, focus on a process of shared vision development to ensure wider engagement with and ownership of the EC’s FOOD 2030 policy framework.
- **Phase 2: Developing Roadmaps (M10-16):** City Labs will formulate educational needs to support R&I and R&I agendas at city level that will contribute to transforming the food system, whereas Policy Labs will develop ‘national transformation agendas’, including researchers, policy makers, consumers, entrepreneurs, etc. These will form input for the EU Think Tank, who will advise on the development of supported food systems research programmes that prioritise the R&I themes and approaches required to transform the European food system.
- **Phase 3: Action Planning and Training (M16-36):** The EU Think Tank will bring in and discuss good practices of policy alignment, barriers and drivers, and will foster knowledge transfer from regional and national level towards the European and global level. This knowledge will be a cornerstone for strategic advice regarding R&I policies and scientific input to thematic policies throughout the Food Chain at EU and global level (e.g. circular bio-economy, Common Agricultural Policy, SDGs, COP21). The experiences of the Policy Labs and City Labs will be discussed within the EU Think Tank and used as an input for further strategy development.
- **Phase 4: Scaling up and Continuity (M26-36):** The EU Think Tank will work towards a blueprint for global collaboration on the food system that builds on existing initiatives as well as on research and innovation strategies to deliver impact on the societal challenge of FNS and related SDGs and COP21 commitments.

The above phases correspond to **WP5 Policy coherence and programme alignment** and **WP6 Building competences on food systems R&I and RRI** of the project. In line with this, members of the EU Think Tank are expected to give input to the **Policy Lab coordinators** (part of WP5) and the **City Lab coordinators** (part of WP6), who will be present during the EU Think Tank meetings (except for the first meeting in June). More specifically, City and Policy Lab coordinators will present their progress and ask the advice of the EU Think Tank for their work. The Think Tank will also be asked to translate the activities and findings of the City Labs to recommendations for EU policies.

In addition to them, members of the Think Tank are expected to **give input to and advice on the** project activities on ‘*Mapping of trends in food systems and related R&I policy frameworks*’ (WP2), ‘*Identification of showcases*’ (WP3), and ‘*Exploration of roadmaps for R&I breakthroughs*’ (WP4); Relevant WP leaders will be present during the EU Think Tank meetings as and when necessary.

Table 1. Proposed issues to discuss

Year	Proposed issues to discuss
First year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Terms of Reference (ToR) and trends (input for WP2) ○ Visions and vision development, showcases and breakthroughs (input for WP2, WP3, WP4)
Second year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Pathways to breakthroughs and transformation agendas (input for WP4 and WP5) ○ Success factors and prototyping (input for WP5, WP6)
Third year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Results of the Pilots (WP5, WP6, Policy Lab and City Lab coordinators) ○ Upscaling, continuity and strategy development <p>During the third year the EU Think Tank will work on global collaboration that builds on the existing initiatives and on R&I strategies to deliver impact on the societal challenge of FNS and related SDGs/COP21 commitments.</p>

The above mentioned topics will be discussed also considering relevant efforts in European level. This includes, among others, the efforts and outputs of the SCAR Food Systems Strategic Working Group.

Finally, the EU Think Tank may be asked to provide recommendations or input to outreach activities of the FIT4FOOD2030 project. For example, the EC is asking the FIT4FOOD2030 project to make hold workshops on topics such as Responsible Research and Innovation and Food Systems in Brussels. The EU Think Tank may be asked to provide advice on the topics of workshops to be organized and experts to be invited. They may also be invited to serve as experts in those workshops as well. The EC may also ask the EU Think Tank to deliver recommendations in different areas of FOOD 2030, in particular in the process of preparations and execution of Horizon Europe, which is the next research and innovation framework programme of the European Commission¹. Some of the key elements of Horizon Europe's timeline and possible requests from the EU Think Tank for recommendations in the context of FOOD 2030 are provided below:

- June 2018 – The Report of the EC FOOD 2030 Independent Expert Group → Commenting on how the recommendations of the expert group potentially link to or fit with the strategies or agendas of different organisations and/or fields present at the EU Think Tank
- September/October 2018 – Developing strategic programming for 4 years → providing policy briefs on relevant topics to the strategic programme
- First quarter of 2019 – Public consultation of the strategic programme → replying to and/or disseminating the call for the public consultation
- June 2019 – Work Programme for 2021-2022 → providing policy briefs or though pieces on possible topics that should be present at the work programme (both thematic topics and cross sectional issues)

3. Roles within the EU Think Tank

The group will be **chaired** by a member of the expert group. He/she will be nominated by the FIT4FOOD2030 project coordinator with the agreement of the EC and put forward for approval of the members of the EU Think Tank at the first meeting.

The Chairperson will set the broad orientation for the group, define meeting agendas in collaboration with the EU Think Tank secretariat and the EC and will ensure that the overall timetable is respected.

Members of the EU Think Tank are expected to:

- Prepare for the EU Think Tank meetings (six in total) in Brussels on the basis of an agenda created by a collaborative effort between the EU Think Tank secretariat, the Chairperson of the EU Think Tank and the EC, and the short background documents provided by the EU Think Tank secretariat;
- Contribute actively and substantially to the work at meetings in Brussels and in communications between meetings.

Further roles of the Chairperson and the Members will be identified in the due course of the project.

¹ For more on Horizon Europe: https://ec.europa.eu/info/designing-next-research-and-innovation-framework-programme/what-shapes-next-framework-programme_en

4. Approach and Methodology

The EU Think Tank will receive necessary input in the following ways:

Firstly, the EU Think Tank will build upon results and findings of the Horizon 2020 Commission Expert Group on FOOD 2030². Findings from this expert group will function as basis for the EU Think Tank. The Commission Expert Group on FOOD 2030 was formed to assist the EC with the development of the FOOD 2030 policy framework, with a specific focus on the exploration and formulation of potential future R&I policy recommendations and actions as well as their potential impacts. This group was active between July 2017 and May 2018.

Secondly, depending on the project phase, at each meeting, the EU Think Tank members will be presented with the findings and/or topics to be discussed from various WPs of FIT4FOOD2030. Depending on the agenda, the members will receive relevant (short) background documents prior to meetings. Moreover, WP leaders of the topics to be discussed, as well as Policy and City Lab coordinators will be present during (a number of) the meetings to shortly present their findings and facilitate discussions.

Relevant policy officers from the EC will be available during the EU Think Tank meetings, and may want to discuss specific topics on FOOD 2030 with the members of the EU Think Tank.

Members of the EU Think Tank will have access to relevant documents via the file sharing platform *Edugroepen*, including the FIT4FOOD2030 project summary, the report of the FOOD 2030 Expert Group, SCAR Foresight studies, relevant project deliverables, and any other relevant background documents.

Notes shall be taken during all EU Think Tank meetings by an appointed member of the Secretariat of the EU Think Tank, which will be run by the VU Amsterdam, led by Prof. dr. Jacqueline Broerse as the Coordinator of the FIT4FOOD2030 project. Minutes shall be sent in draft form to all members of the EU Think Tank within **15 working days** after the meeting.

The draft minutes shall be considered as accepted, if, within **15 working days** from sending, no member has objected in writing to the secretariat of the EU Think Tank.

The EU Think Tank secretariat will draft short documents on some of the important topics discussed at the meeting and provide it to the EU Think Tank members for their comments, feedback and approval. These documents can be, for example, in form of policy briefs or position statements to put important issues into the attention of the EC for Horizon Europe. The members will be expected to respond to those draft documents in 15 working days.

5. Confidentiality: Non-disclosure agreement

Members of the EU Think Tank shall respect the confidentiality of the EU Think Tank meetings and shall sign the non-disclosure agreement which will be sent to all members prior to the first EU Think Tank meeting.

² Report of the EC FOOD 2030 Independent Expert Group: *Recipe for change. An agenda for a climate-smart and sustainable food system for a healthy Europe*: <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d0c725de-6f7c-11e8-9483-01aa75ed71a1/language-en> or the Executive Summary: https://ec.europa.eu/research/bioeconomy/pdf/publications/ES_recipe_for_change.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none

6. Timeframe

The duration of the EU Think is set till November 2020, including six meetings.

Table 2. Timeframe

EU Think Tank meeting	Date
First year	
First meeting	Month 6 – 26 June 2018
Second meeting	Month 10 – 25 October 2018
Second year	
Third meeting	Month 17 – March 2019
Fourth meeting	Month 23 – September 2019
Third year	
Fifth meeting	Month 29 – March 2020
Sixth meeting	Month 35 – September 2020

7. Composition and expert profiles

Experts were selected during an iterative process of four months, during which suggestions and feedback of the EC and the FIT4FOOD2030 project consortium were taken into account (for a list of the consortium members, please refer to the project summary provided earlier).

The following criteria were used to select potential members:

- **Current and former function(s):** referring to an inclusion of experts working or having experience within academia, international organisations (including global organisations), governmental organisations, funding agencies, and/or companies;
- **Fields of expertise and connection to FOOD 2030:** referring to experts having experience or having specific knowledge of the sectors covered by FOOD 2030, including *food systems; food value chain from production (agriculture, fisheries and aquaculture) to food processing, packaging, distribution, waste streams, consumers and communities, (mal) nutrition and health, R&I and R&I policies, impact assessment and evaluation, and agricultural economics*. In other words, a connection to one or more of the FOOD 2030 themes, including 1) *Nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets*, 2) *Climate smart and environmentally sustainable food systems*, 3) *Circularity and resource efficiency*, and 4) *Innovation and empowerment of communities*;

The following aspects were taken also into account:

- To have balance of different expertise areas;
- To include some members from the Commission Expert Group on FOOD 2030, in order to ensure continuity;
- To have gender balance;
- To have diversity in nationalities and organisations represented.

An overview of the members of the EU Think Tank is provided below in table 4.

Table 4. Profiles of the members of the EU Think Tank

Expert member	Profile
<p>João Breda</p>	<p>João Breda works in the Division of Noncommunicable Diseases and Life-course at the World Health Organisation (WHO)/Europe. He provides support to the 53 Member States in the WHO European Region on the implementation of the European Charter on Counteracting Obesity and evaluates their progress. His team is responsible for the world's largest and most comprehensive surveillance mechanism for childhood obesity. Before joining WHO he was the Portuguese focal point to WHO/Europe for nutrition and physical activity, and the High Level Group on Nutrition and Physical Activity and the European Platform on Diet, Nutrition and Physical Activity of the EU. Dr Breda was the first coordinator of the national platform against obesity under the Portuguese Ministry of Health. He worked as a public health nutritionist at the general health directorate in Ministry. He was the Head of the Nutrition Department at Atlantic University in Lisbon and lecturer and researcher at the Escola Superior Agrária de Coimbra (ESAC), the University of the Algarve and the School of Hospitality and Culinary Arts in Coimbra. For more informaion, please click here.</p>
<p>Jean Cahill</p>	<p>Jean Cahill is responsible for pre-award research development and strategic planning in Food & Health Sciences as well as promoting research and enterprise activities at the Dublin Institute of Technology (DIT) in Research News and on the Dublin Research and Enterprise (DRE) website. She has worked as an evaluator for over 25 years for the European Commission including Marie Curie; Food; SME; and COST programmes. She was a member of the Societal Challenge 2 Expert Advisory Group and the H2020 Advisory Group on Gender from 2014 to 2016 and the Science with and for Society H2020 Expert advisory group until from 2016 to 2018. She represents DIT on the National Athena Swan Steering Committee dedicated to improving gender equality in Higher Education in Ireland. She has previously worked for 12 years as a Senior Food Researcher as PI for a large number of EU funded consumer research studies; worked with food companies across Ireland as part of her roles as Manager of the DIT Food Product Development Centre and Head of Innovation & Industry Services. She has been a Director of Bord Bia the State Food Marketing Board and the National Standards Authority of Ireland. She has completed undergraduate degrees in Science; Food Science & Technology; and Law and holds a Masters degree in Food Science & Technology. For more information, please click here.</p>
<p>Carolyn Callenius</p>	<p>Carolyn Callenius is Managing Director of the Hohenheim Research Center for Global Food Security and Ecosystems (GFE). The main tasks of the GFE are to promote and support collaborative research projects on global food security and nutrition, planetary boundaries, climate change and adaptation, ecosystem services, and development oriented agricultural research. The center promotes and supports international research cooperation, inter- and transdisciplinary research, and science-policy-interface. Before joining the GFE, Carolyn Callenius worked for 25 years with faith based development organizations in Germ any as Senior Policy Advisor on the Right to Food, as Coordinator of a Campaign on World Food Security and as Gender Advisor. She received her M.Sc. degree in Agricultural Sciences from the University of Hohenheim, with the focus on rural socio-economics and agriculture in the tropics and subtropics. For more information, please click here.</p>
<p>Patrick Caron</p>	<p>Patrick Caron is currently the International Director of Montpellier University of Excellence (MUSE). He is since November 2015 the Chair of the High Level Panel of Experts (HLPE) of the Committee on World Food Security (CFS). He was also until recently (2010-2016) the Director of the French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development (CIRAD), that he joined in 1988. He is a veterinary doctor and a researcher in geography and his works relate to the analysis of the role of agriculture and livestock in rural transformation. He specially looks at the trans-scales combination of processes and actions (from household to international levels) which underpin changes at territorial level, and, in return, at the capacity of territory to play a regulatory function. He is also member of many institutional and interinstitutional bodies, e.g. he is charing the Scientific Council of AgroParisTech. For more information, please click here.</p>

Expert member	Profile
<p>Zoya Damianova</p>	<p>Zoya Damianova is the Programme Director of the Applied Research and Communications Fund, Bulgaria. Since 1997 Zoya has been involved in several sectoral foresight projects (agriculture, energy, and environment), as well as in projects focused on public engagement with research. Recently, she coordinated the CASI project (Public Participation in Developing a Common Framework for Assessment and Management of Sustainable Innovation, Jan 2014 – Jun 2017, FP7). She is currently working on (i) Responsible Research and Innovation in Practice, a project aiming to understand the barriers and drivers to the successful implementation of RRI in research conducting and research funding organisations, (ii) research infrastructures in the Danube Region, and (iii) sustainable energy consumption. Zoya has participated in several working groups at DG RTD of the European Commission: 2010 – 2011, member of the 3rd foresight expert group at the EU Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR FEG3); Jan – Sept 2012, member of International STI cooperation expert group; 2014 – 2015, member of an Expert group on identifying cross-sectoral research priorities at the junction of health, environment and bioeconomy.</p>
<p>Margaret Gill</p>	<p>Margaret Gill is a former Chief Scientific Adviser to the Scottish Government on Rural Affairs and the Environment. She is Professor of Integrated Land Use at the University of Aberdeen, and also chair of the CGIAR (a global partnership that unites organizations engaged in research for a food-secured future) Independent Science and Partnership Council (ISPC). She also chairs a Science Advisory Panel for the Our Land and Water Challenge programme in New Zealand and chaired the Science Advisory Board of FACCE JPI until June 2017. Her original research career was in animal science, broadening out over time to an interest in the impacts of agriculture on the environment and how science can provide an evidence base to inform policy. She is also a Trustee of GALVmed a charity which seeks to make animal products affordable for smallholder livestock owners in developing countries. For more information, please click here.</p>
<p>Mirjana Gurinovic</p>	<p>Mirjana Gurinovic MD. PhD Nutrition, Scientific Research Advisor, FAO Nutrition consultant, research team leader at the Centre of Research Excellence in Nutrition and Metabolism, Institute for Medical Research, University of Belgrade, Serbia, www.srbnutrition.info is recognized public health nutrition scientists, actively engaged in research on nutrition, food composition data bases, public health nutrition epidemiology, harmonization of the dietary intake assessment, nutrient recommendations, food and nutrition policy, Sustainable Food Systems for Healthy Diets, nutritional tools development and research infrastructure for food and nutrition research, preschool and schoolchildren nutrition improvement, diet and health and capacity development in food and nutrition specific for CEE countries. She had leading and active role in national and international food and nutrition research projects (EC FP6 and FP7 NoE projects, including EURRECA, EuroFIR, BaseFood, CHANCE, EuroFIR-Nexus, BACCHUSS, ODIN, four EFSA projects and member of project advisory board in Euro DISH project). Dr. Gurinović is a Chair of the Network for Capacity development in Nutrition in CEE Countries (CAPNUTRA) (www.capnutra.org) which was established in 2005 in FAO in Budapest and contributed to food & nutrition capacity development in this region. She has over 300 published peer-review papers, abstracts, and reports in national and international journals. Dr. Gurinovic is a member of a number of professional associations including: Europe Expert Group on 'Evaluation of New Methods for Dietary Intake Assessment', EFSA Scientific Network on Food Consumption Data, "EU Think Tank" FOOD 2030, World Public Health Nutrition Association (WPHNA), Nutrition Expert Group in European Heart Network where she contributed to the European food and nutrition recommendations for cardiovascular diseases prevention. She is research professor at the integrated food science module for PhD students at the University of Belgrade. For more information, please click here, or here.</p>
<p>Liisa Lähteenmäki</p>	<p>Liisa Lähteenmäki (MSc in Nutrition; PhD in Psychology) is Professor of Consumer Behaviour and Food Choice at Aarhus University. She is part of the MAPP Centre - Research on Value Creation in the Food Sector for Consumers, Industry and Society, which has been evaluated as one of the leading centres on consumer and innovation research on food sector. Her research areas include consumer behaviour (e.g. consumer decision making, behaviour change mechanisms) with special interest in food-related behaviours, sustainable and responsible behaviours (e.g. food waste), and integrating consumer insight in innovation processes (e.g. acceptability of new innovations and technologies, communication challenges). Professor Lähteenmäki has acted as an expert in evaluating research proposal in several national and international committees and acts currently as one of co-executive editors in journal <i>Appetite</i>. For more information, please click here.</p>

Expert member	Profile
<p>Tim Lang</p>	<p>Tim Lang has been Professor of Food Policy at City University London's Centre for Food Policy since 2002. He founded the Centre in 1994. After a PhD in social psychology at Leeds University, he became a hill farmer in the 1970s in the Forest of Bowland, Lancashire which shifted his attention to food policy, where it has been ever since. For years, he's engaged in academic and public research and debate about its direction, locally to globally. His abiding interest is how policy addresses the mixed challenge of being food for the environment, health, social justice, and citizens. What is a good food system? How is ours measured and measuring up? He has been a consultant to the WHO (eg auditing the Global Top 25 Food Companies on food and health 2005), Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) (eg co-chairing the FAO definition of sustainable diets 2010) and UNEP (eg co-writing its 2012 Avoiding Future Famines report). He has been a special advisor to four House of Commons Select Committee inquiries, two on food standards (1998-9 & 1999), globalisation (2000) and obesity (2003-04), and a consultant on food security to the Royal Institute of International Affairs (Chatham House 2007-09). He was a Commissioner on the UK Government's Sustainable Development Commission (2006-11). For more information, please click here.</p>
<p>André Laperrière</p>	<p>André Laperrière Executive Director Global Open Data for Agriculture and Nutrition (GODAN) Mr. André Laperrière joined the Global Open Data for Agriculture and Nutrition (GODAN) initiative as its first Executive Director, in September 2015. During his career, Mr. Laperrière has led/managed numerous projects on behalf of large Private Corporations and subsequently, within the United Nations and the World Bank. In this context he played a senior role in the design and the implementation of major reforms within a number of agencies such as the International Criminal Court (ICC), the WHO and UNICEF. He has extensive work experience in the Americas, Caribbean, Africa, Europe and the Middle East, in particular in developing countries and in conflict/post conflict environments. Before joining GODAN, Mr. Laperrière was Deputy Chief Executive Officer at the Global Environment Facility (GEF) in Washington DC. Among other positions, he has also been the first Executive Director of the Trust Fund for Victims at the International Criminal Court (ICC), Director of the Administration and Finance Division in the WHO, and Coordinator for reconstruction and rehabilitation activities under the responsibility of UNICEF in Iraq. Prior to his career in the UN, Mr. Laperrière was Director in the International Services of Price Waterhouse. For more information, please click here or here.</p>
<p>Carlo Mango</p>	<p>Carlo Mango started his career in 1991, working for university-enterprise research consortiums in the field of R&D and technology transfer. He has been a coordinator of several international research projects and project manager of a significant number of technology transfer projects in cooperation with leading industrial partners. Carlo Mango has been working as Director of the Scientific Research Department of Fondazione Cariplo (one of the biggest grant-providing foundations in Europe, based in Milan) since the beginning of its funding activity in February 2001. He is in charge of the entire cycle of strategic planning, programme design and management of Fondazione Cariplo's research, education and technology transfer initiatives. He is also involved in several international scientific committees, boards of directors of research foundations and is co-founder and an independent member of the Investment Committee of TT Venture Fund, an Italian VC fund focused on early stage science-based businesses (a mission-related investment subscribed to by several Italian banking foundations). For more information, please click here.</p>
<p>John Ryder</p>	<p>John Ryder currently heads up the Products, Markets and Trade Branch of the Fisheries and Aquaculture Department in the Food and Agriculture Organization in Rome. For the majority of his career, John has worked in post-harvest fisheries in national and international organisations in various parts of the world and has spent most of the last 25 years in international development, working for DFID, the FAO and as a consultant. Aside from his current management responsibilities, he tries to keep his hand in food safety, export compliance and market access and trade issues. For more information, please click here.</p>
<p>Roberta Sonnino</p>	<p>Roberta Sonnino is a Professor in the School of Geography and Planning (Cardiff University, UK), where she has been involved in international research on food security, urban food strategies and governance and public food policies. In recent years, Professor Sonnino has acted as a commentator to print and broadcast media organizations in Italy, Finland, Denmark, Spain and the UK and has been an advisor on food policy for the European Commission, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, the Welsh Government and the Soil Association. Professor Sonnino is the Director of the Research Centre for Sustainable Urban and Regional Food (SURF) at Cardiff University. For more information, please click here.</p>

Expert member	Profile
<p>Gerda Verburg</p>	<p>Since August 2016, Gerda Verburg from the Netherlands has served as United Nations Assistant Secretary-General and Coordinator of the Scaling Up Nutrition (SUN) Movement. She was appointed by the UN Secretary-General based on her extensive experience in politics and international cooperation. In 2008, following her appointment the previous year as Minister of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality of the Netherlands, she was elected as Chair of the UN Commission on Sustainable Development (CSD 17). From 2011, she served as Permanent Representative of the Netherlands to the she served as Permanent Representative of the Netherlands to the United Nations Rome-based agencies (FAO, IFAD and WFP). In 2013, she was elected as Chair of the UN Committee on World Food Security (CFS), and in 2014 she was appointed as Chair of the Agenda Council for Food and Nutrition of the World Economic Forum (WEF). For more information, please click here or here.</p>
<p>Henk Westhoek</p>	<p>Henk Westhoek (1959) is since 2001 the program manager for Food and Agriculture of the Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (PBL), which works at the science-policy interface. Before joining PBL, he worked for 10 years for the Dutch Ministry of Agriculture on issues related to livestock and the environment. He has also worked in Indonesia and Rwanda. He has a MSc in Soil Science and Plant nutrition from Wageningen University. He has been involved in numerous national and international assessments and scenario-studies. He was lead author of reports as the Protein Puzzle (2011), Nitrogen on the table (2015), Food systems and natural resources (UNEP-IRP, 2016), Food in a green light (EEA, 2017) and Recipe for Change (report EU Expert group). For more information, please click here.</p>

Abbreviations

DG RTD	Directorate General for Research and Innovation
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FIT4FOOD2030	Fostering Integration and Transformation for FOOD 2030
FNS	Food and Nutrition Security
R&I	Research and Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SCAR	Standing Committee of Agricultural Research
ToR	Terms of Reference
UN	United Nations
WP	Work Package